

THE CONCEPTUAL IMPORTANCE OF SHAPING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF YOUTH

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Abstract: The article addresses the issue of shaping the spiritual and moral education of youth, emphasizing the conceptual importance of "The Conceptual Importance of Shaping the Spiritual and Moral Education of Youth" through providing scientifically grounded definitions. The article discusses the significance of education as a consistently crucial issue for every period and society, emphasizing that recommendations for shaping the spiritual and moral education of youth should be based on national values.

Keywords: Education, spiritual and moral education, comprehensive education, youth education, knowledge and wisdom, high virtues, and excellence.

Introduction

In today's society, a wide range of initiatives are being undertaken to contribute to the development of our country, promoting social progress and ensuring sustainable growth. However, the attention given to the moral and ethical upbringing of the youth is not sufficient. In this context, the conceptual importance of further elevating the spiritual and moral education of the youth is becoming evident. The role and significance of knowledge and education are crucial in shaping the moral and ethical development of the youth.

"A science that calls people to goodness and steers them away from evil is indeed a valuable one. Books that illustrate the goodness of good people and the evil of evil people with evidence and examples are considered moral books. Studying and practicing the science of ethics, individuals understand their identity, their purpose for the sake of truth, and the endeavors they undertake in this world. A person who is not self-aware remains ignorant of knowledge, principles, good people, good things, and the value of good deeds. Recognizing one's flaws, repenting, and striving to abandon them make a person truly noble and virtuous. Our honorable Prophet, peace be upon him, said: 'Among the actions placed on the Scale (of Judgment), there is nothing weightier than good character. A believer with good character will not be surpassed by one who fasts and prays but has no control over their tongue or commits aggression.'

Humans consist of two complex elements: the body and the soul. The body perceives external things through the eyes, while the soul distinguishes between good and evil, illuminates from darkness, and rejects ignorance. Both the body and the soul have their own aspects, whether good or evil.

The appearance of the body is visible to everyone at all times. However, the appearance of the soul is invisible to the eyes, a hidden aspect that can only be measured with intellect. People are considered human based on their character. If a person grows up without discipline and morality in their youth, lacking ethics, then such individuals, despite proclaiming "Allahu Akbar," are like those who stretch their hands towards the stars while lying on the ground.

Our beloved Prophet, peace be upon him, said: "If you hear that someone has left their place to go in a certain direction, you may believe it. However, if you hear that someone's character has changed, do not believe it"¹.

In today's globalizing world, the reality is that a serious struggle for intellectual and moral development is taking place everywhere on the planet. This struggle, manifesting itself in both violent and civilized forms, requires each of us to contribute to scrutinizing the global processes with reason and reflection, evaluating the ongoing events in the world with intellect and contemplation. Notably, the conceptual importance of further elevating the spiritual and moral education of the youth is emphasized in the presidential decree dated May 3, 2019, titled "Additional Measures to Enhance the Effectiveness of Spiritual and Educational Affairs" and in the address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 25, 2020. The Republic Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment "Ma'rifat," along with various ministries and state and public organizations, is actively involved in implementing tasks outlined in videoconference meetings aimed at strengthening cooperation between state and community organizations.

The statement by our country's leader that "If the body of society is the economy, its soul and spirit are spirituality," resonates with the essence of the call of Hazrat Navoi to the third Renaissance wall, expressing the determination of our people to create a civilization with upbringing, good manners, intellect, knowledge, and spirituality as powerful and spiritual sources. Therefore, the existence of the economy as the body of a society with high spirituality infuses life, spirit, vitality, and boundless creative power.

From a philosophical standpoint, spirituality and knowledge have always been a boundless power, a source of happiness, peace, prosperity, the

¹ A. Avloni. "Turkic Gulistan or Ethics" Ziyouz.uz. 2012.

foundation of mutual support, and the elevation of the soul that elevates the heart. Because it has been a blessing for our nation, people, and individuals to live based on high virtues, guided by moral principles, and always striving for goodness in the path of ethics, to make this world flourish, and to be beautiful.

"Our constant concern is another important issue - the etiquette, behavior, the way of speaking of our youth, in a word, their connection with the outside world. Today the time is changing rapidly. Let everyone not forget this change: who we are, what the great beings invite us to do for our generation, let them always strive to be sincere to themselves. What do we achieve in this regard? Education, education, and only from education"². By the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2019, "On Additional Measures to Increase the Effectiveness of Spiritual and Educational Affairs Sh. Mirziyoyev. "Ensuring social stability, preserving the sanctity of our sacred religion - the requirement of the time" dated June 15, 2017, additional measures were taken regarding additional measures. The systematic organization of spiritual and educational activities in our country, the improvement of the effectiveness of the ongoing activities, the intellectual abilities of the population, especially the youth, the strengthening of their worldview and patriotism, and the cultivation of a mature generation living with a sense of love and loyalty to the homeland are given special attention. Enhancing the impact of spiritual and educational activities, effectively combating internal and external threats and risks, strengthening the intellectual immunity of society, and supporting the activities of the state and public organizations in this regard were among the tasks outlined in the direction of the Ministry and local government bodies. The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was assigned the task of developing the "Comprehensive Concept of Spiritual Education." According to the essence of spiritual and moral education, the connection of human rights with society lies in the fact that it is a powerful source of spiritual and moral upbringing, understanding the responsibility for the civilization level of society, recognizing the national values by society, feeling the responsibility in fulfilling the ideals, norms, and requirements recognized by society, and forming spiritual-moral feelings and qualities. From the perspective of spiritual and moral education, it is necessary to understand the connection of human rights with society in terms of its understanding of the essence of social spirituality, its connection with the spiritual and moral values adopted by society, the

² Shavkat Mirziyoyev. "Ensuring Social Stability, Preserving the Sanctity of Our Sacred Religion - the Requirement of the Time," June 15, 2017.

manifestation of responsibility for spiritual and moral upbringing in society, the embodiment of spiritual and moral values, and the formation of spiritual and moral feelings and qualities.

The concept of education plays a crucial role in providing comprehensive education to young people on all sides to ensure their mature development. Programs and training courses have been developed and implemented to shape virtues and skills such as love for the homeland, national pride, courage, bravery, loyalty, honesty, justice, compassion, conscientiousness, responsibility, valor, honor, and family values like entrepreneurship and family care for boys. Similarly, for girls, programs and training courses have been developed and implemented to instill virtues such as love for the homeland, national pride, industriousness, adaptability, family care, kindness, modesty, neatness, contentment, gratitude, generosity, compassion, mercy, humility, hospitality, friendliness, childhood, tenderness, diplomacy, friendliness among other qualities.

The education concept includes the organization of programs and training courses aimed at developing skills such as leadership, punctuality, etc. in society. There are several risks associated with spiritually and morally educating youth in society. One of them is the internet and social media. In the global context, it is impossible to imagine development without them, but enhancing the ideological immunity in the youth against negative influences is crucial. "In the global context, sources that negatively influence the spiritual development of society, especially young minds not yet formed, on the Internet and social networks are not uncommon. Our Eastern morality and traditions are crucial in protecting us from such negative tendencies." The curriculum of education, considered one of the components of this concept, is particularly engaging for modern students, given their interests and character traits. In each lesson, students are involved in mutual respect, culture, goal-setting, humanity, respect for values, respect for family, loyalty to parents, love for parents, respect for knowledge, a sense of belonging to society, and love for the homeland.

The concept emphasizes the importance of cultivating the feeling of respect for national values as part of spiritual and moral education. "National values play an everlasting role in cultivating national pride, national honor in people." Thus, according to the Comprehensive Concept of Spiritual Education, the growing importance of spiritual and moral education in young people is recognized. It is essential to note that the subsequent stages of the program and schedule will

undoubtedly provide further benefits and contribute significantly to its implementation.

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